

Load Dependent Nanoindentation Studies of Ultrananocrystalline Diamond (UNCD) Thin Films

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Abstract

Ultrananocrystalline diamond (UNCD) films were grown on mirror polished silicon (100) substrates in microwave plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition system [1]. This film has been attracted widely to scientific community due to its attractive thermal and mechanical properties. Unique mechanical properties of this film was governed by ultranano diamond grains of diamond phase embedded with amorphous carbon (a-C) and short ranged crystalline sp^2 phase [1]. Plastic deformation in UNCD films is mainly located at the grain boundary and dislocation processes within the grain are not active due to ultrasmall size grains [2]. It was shown that the stress required for grain boundary sliding is the main mechanism to determine hardness and yield strength in this material [2]. Our experimental results showed high hardness at lower indentation loads which might be related to strain hardening effect (Fig. 1). This effect has been investigated by high pressure Raman spectroscopic studies on UNCD film which confirmed the hardening upon compression [3]. However, hardness decreased at higher indentation loads, which might be associated to mechanical deformation. Increase in elastic modulus is purely governed by rigid sp^3 bonding of ultranano diamond grains and sp^2 bonding of grain boundary phase. Grain boundaries of UNCD film were found to be highly stable and Raman spectra showed reversible behavior upon release of pressure. This explanation can be considered for improved elastic modulus at higher indentation loads.

Figure 1. Load dependent nanoindentation study of UNCD film

Keywords

UNCD film, Load dependence, Nanoindentation

Reference

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